

D1.3 – Ethics & Privacy Management Plan

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D1.3 – Ethics & Privacy Management Plan (due in M6)

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Executive Summary

The D1.3 – Ethics & Privacy Management Plan outlines the framework for the RIS4SEB partners ensuring ethical compliance and effective personal data protection throughout the project. This plan consists of two key sections: the first section details ethical principles and personal data protection standards; the second section presents the specific approaches adopted by each partner institution to align with ethical and privacy guidelines while addressing their unique contexts. By implementing this plan, RIS4SEB partners reaffirm their commitment to upholding the highest ethical standards and responsibly managing personal data, fostering a culture of integrity and accountability in their research activities.

If any RIS4SEB partner identifies an ethics or privacy issue or breach at any point during the project, they should immediately notify the coordinator at VSE. The coordinator will then present the matter to the Steering Committee for further action. You can contact the coordinators at ris4seb@vse.cz.

Key definitions¹

The following section clarifies some important terms and definitions used in the GDPR.

GDPR: The General Data Protection Regulation is a European Union law that came into effect on May 25, 2018. It governs how organizations collect, store, and process personal data of individuals within the EU. GDPR aims to give individuals greater control over their personal information and ensure that companies handle this data responsibly, transparently, and securely. Key principles include consent, data minimization, transparency, and the right to access or erase personal data. Non-compliance can result in significant fines, making GDPR a critical regulation for businesses worldwide.

Data Protection Authority: DPA is an independent public authority responsible for overseeing and enforcing data protection laws and ensuring compliance with the regulation. DPAs handle complaints, conduct investigations, issue fines and sanctions, and provide guidance on data protection matters. They serve as a point of contact for individuals seeking to exercise their data protection rights and for organizations needing advice on compliance with GDPR. Each EU member state has its own DPA, and they collectively contribute to a consistent application of data protection standards across the EU.

Data Protection Officer: DPO is a designated individual within an organization responsible for overseeing data protection and privacy compliance.

Personal Data: Any information related to an identified or identifiable natural person (data subject). This includes names, identification numbers, location data, online identifiers, or one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that person.

Data Controller: The entity (person, company, or organization) that determines the purposes and means of processing personal data. The controller is responsible for ensuring compliance with GDPR.

Data Processor: A natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or other body that processes personal data on behalf of the data controller. Processors have specific legal obligations under GDPR.

Processing: Any operation or set of operations performed on personal data, whether by automated means or not. This includes collection, recording, organization, structuring, storage, adaptation, alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination, or making available, alignment, combination, restriction, erasure, or destruction of data.

Consent: A freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of the data subject's wishes, by which they signify agreement to the processing of their personal data. Consent must be verifiable and can be withdrawn at any time.

Data Subject: The individual to whom the personal data relates. Under GDPR, data subjects have specific rights regarding their data.

¹ Source: GDPR.eu, "Chapter 1 of the GDPR," accessed Oct. 11, 2024, <https://gdpr.eu/tag/chapter-1/>

Data Breach: A breach of security leading to the accidental or unlawful destruction, loss, alteration, unauthorized disclosure of, or access to, personal data transmitted, stored, or otherwise processed.

Right to be Forgotten: Also known as the right to erasure, this allows the data subject to request the deletion of their personal data when it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected, or when the data subject withdraws consent.

Right to Access: The right of data subjects to obtain confirmation from the controller as to whether their personal data is being processed, and if so, access to that personal data along with information on how it is being used.

Right to Data Portability: The right to receive personal data concerning the data subject, which they have provided to a controller, in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format, and the right to transmit that data to another controller without hindrance.

Right to Rectification: The right that allows individuals to request the correction or updating of their personal data if it is inaccurate or incomplete. This right ensures that individuals can have their data amended to accurately reflect their current circumstances. Organizations must respond to such requests promptly and make the necessary changes, thereby maintaining the accuracy and reliability of personal data they hold.

Right to Restriction: The right that allows individuals to request the limitation of processing their personal data under certain circumstances. Specifically, individuals can request restriction when they contest the accuracy of the data, when processing is unlawful, but they oppose deletion, when the data is no longer needed for processing but is required for legal claims, or when they object to processing based on legitimate interests. During the restriction period, the data can be stored but not further processed, ensuring that the individual's data is protected while resolving any issues or disputes.

Right to Object: The right to object under the GDPR allows individuals to challenge and oppose the processing of their personal data based on legitimate interests, direct marketing, or processing for scientific or historical research purposes. Individuals can exercise this right at any time, and organizations must cease processing the data unless they can demonstrate compelling legitimate grounds that override the individual's interests, rights, and freedoms, or if the processing is necessary for legal claims. This right ensures that individuals have control over how their data is used, particularly in situations where they may not have previously been consulted.

Purpose Limitation: An overarching privacy principle stating that personal data must be collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes. In other words, personal data collection should be for a clear and specific purpose.

Data Accuracy: Refers to the quality of personal data being correct, complete, and up-to-date, ensuring it reflects the true situation of the data subject.

Storage Limitation: A principle that mandates personal data should only be retained for as long as necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. Once the data is no longer needed, it must be either deleted or anonymized.

Data minimization: A principle that organizations must collect and process only the personal data that is adequate, relevant, and limited to what is necessary for the specific purpose. This principle ensures that data collected is sufficient to fulfill its intended purpose without being excessive or irrelevant, thereby minimizing the risk of unnecessary data accumulation and protecting individuals' privacy.

Introduction

The D1.3 – Ethics & Privacy Management Plan is a comprehensive framework designed to ensure that the project **Enhancing Research and Innovation Synergies for Schools of Economics and Business (RIS4SEB)** upholds the needed standards of ethical conduct and privacy protection in all aspects of its operations. This plan serves as a guiding document for navigating the complex landscape of data management, addressing the ethical implications of our practices, and safeguarding the privacy of individuals whose information we manage.

The Ethics & Privacy Management Plan is a key project deliverable that outlines the procedures and guidelines to ensure ethical compliance and data privacy throughout the project. It provides a framework for handling sensitive data, ensuring transparency, safeguarding individual rights, and aligning with legal standards, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). This deliverable is part of Work Package 1 and is led by the Prague University of Economics and Business (VSE). It is structured in two parts, presenting two complementary outputs:

- **Guidelines for the RIS4SEB project to comply with ethics and eGDPR: Designed to be used by RIS4SEB participants to ensure full compliance with ethical standards and GDPR.**
- **Ethical and privacy principles: Tailored specifically for each university involved in the project.**

The RIS4SEB project is a Horizon Europe initiative aimed at strengthening synergies between non-centrally managed programmes and centrally managed programmes. The Pathway to Synergies initiative capitalizes on the know-how developed by partners under non-centrally managed programmes, such as ERDF or Interreg, and applies this knowledge to international research programmes, such as Horizon Europe. This effort helps firmly establish the project consortium's presence on the European Research Area (ERA) map.

The RIS4SEB project brings together widening partners — Prague University of Economics and Business, Kaunas University of Technology, and Estonian Business School — who have successfully secured ERDF, Interreg, or similar indirect EU projects. This collaboration is supported by the highly experienced non-widening partner, Bocconi University, aiming to increase success in international research projects within the Horizon Europe framework.

The overall objective of the RIS4SEB project is to design and pilot three strategies that facilitate synergies between Horizon Europe and other national or regional funds. These strategies aim to strengthen the internationalization of R&I widening actors, develop human resources, and improve research management capacity. The project achieves this through capacity-building activities, including networks analysis, infrastructure sharing, and upskilling of research managers and researchers, ultimately submitting at least four joint Horizon Europe projects. By the end of the project, policy recommendations will be developed to openly share gained knowledge with regional and national Managing Authorities, fostering synergies among various EU funding programmes.

Through the D1.3 – Ethics & Privacy Management Plan, the RIS4SEB project ensures not only compliance with relevant laws and regulations but also fosters a culture of ethical decision-making. The plan highlights principles, policies, and procedures that guide data handling and privacy protection, ensuring that all project contributors follow best practices in these areas. Beyond legal compliance, the plan emphasizes the importance of ethical responsibility, requiring a proactive approach to transparency, respect for individual rights, and risk mitigation.

Through the implementation of this Ethics & Privacy Management Plan, the RIS4SEB project not only protects the privacy of individuals but also reinforces its reputation as a trusted and ethical entity in the research ecosystem.

1. Ethics

Beneficiaries must comply with ethical principles and applicable EU, international, and national laws. This includes the **EU Charter of Fundamental Rights** and the **European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms**, including its Supplementary Protocols.

Key Ethical Principles²

The following ethical principles are fundamental to ensuring responsible and ethical conduct:

- a) **Respect for human dignity and integrity:** Ensuring that all academic, research, and administrative activities respect the inherent dignity of individuals involved.
- b) **Honesty and transparency:** Maintaining clear communication with all participants, including research subjects, and ensuring free and informed consent (or assent where relevant), particularly in research processes.
- c) **Protection of vulnerable persons:** Paying special attention to protecting individuals who may be at risk due to factors such as age, socioeconomic status, or health conditions.
- d) **Privacy and confidentiality:** Safeguarding personal information of students, faculty, staff, and research participants, and ensuring strict confidentiality in handling all personal data, in compliance with applicable privacy laws and regulations.
- e) **Justice and inclusiveness:** Promoting fairness and inclusivity in research, education, and university operations, ensuring equal access to resources and opportunities for all members of the university community.
- f) **Minimizing harm and maximizing benefit:** Striving to minimize any potential harm while enhancing positive outcomes for all stakeholders, including students, research participants, and the broader community.
- g) **Environmental protection:** Respecting the environment and future generations by integrating sustainability principles into research, education, and campus operations to minimize negative environmental impacts.
- h) **Non-discrimination:** Prohibiting discrimination on various grounds, including sex, race, ethnicity, and disability. All individuals should have equal opportunities.

Compliance with both legal frameworks and ethical guidelines ensures that the project not only meets regulatory requirements but also contributes to a positive and equitable environment for all participants.

² Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, 2012. *EUR-Lex*. [online] Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:12012P/TXT> [Accessed 11 Oct. 2024]

2. GDPR Rules of the European Union

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) of the European Union sets forth comprehensive guidelines and obligations for organizations handling personal data. In the context of the D1.3 Ethics and Privacy Management Plan, these rules are essential to ensuring that all data processing activities are conducted in a manner that respects the privacy and rights of individuals.

Key Data Protection Principles

RIS4SEB will have to comply with the European regulations and norms related to personal data protection and privacy. The two main normative sources that will be considered and focus on are:

- Regulation EU/679/2016 (GDPR)
- Privacy and Electronic Communications Directive 2002/58/EC (ePrivacy Directive)

Here are key principles derived from these 2 regulations:

I. Key Principles of GDPR (Regulation (EU) 2016/679)³:

1. **Lawfulness, Fairness, and Transparency:** Personal data must be processed legally, fairly, and transparently. Data subjects must be informed about how their data is used.
2. **Purpose Limitation:** Data should only be collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not processed further in a manner incompatible with those purposes.
3. **Data Minimization:** Only the personal data necessary for the specific purpose should be collected.
4. **Accuracy:** Personal data must be accurate and, where necessary, kept up to date.
5. **Storage Limitation:** Personal data should not be kept longer than necessary for the purposes it was collected for.
6. **Integrity and Confidentiality (Security):** Data must be processed securely to prevent unauthorized access, loss, or damage.
7. **Accountability:** Data controllers are responsible for compliance and must demonstrate adherence to GDPR principles.

i. Key Principles of the ePrivacy Directive (Directive 2002/58/EC)⁴:

1. **Confidentiality of Communications:** Electronic communications must be kept confidential. Any interception or monitoring of communications is prohibited without consent or legal justification.

³ GDPR.eu, "What is GDPR, the EU's Data Protection Law?" accessed on Oct. 11, 2024, <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>

⁴ European ePrivacy Regulation, "Welcome to the European ePrivacy Regulation," accessed Oct. 11, 2024, <https://www.european-eprivacy-regulation.com/>

2. **Consent for Cookies and Tracking:** Websites must obtain informed consent from users before storing or accessing cookies or similar tracking technologies on their devices.
3. **Data Security:** Providers of publicly available electronic communication services must ensure the security of their services and inform users of any risks.
4. **Spam and Direct Marketing:** Unsolicited commercial communications, such as emails or SMS, require prior consent (opt-in) from recipients. Exceptions may apply for existing customer relationships.
5. **Location Data:** The processing of location data other than traffic data (e.g., mobile phone geolocation) is only allowed if the data is anonymized or users have given consent.
6. **Traffic Data:** Data related to the routing, duration, or timing of a communication should be erased or anonymized once it's no longer needed for billing or transmission, except with user consent.

Interplay Between GDPR and ePrivacy Directive:

- **GDPR** provides general rules on personal data protection applicable across various sectors.
- **ePrivacy Directive** complements the GDPR by focusing specifically on privacy in electronic communications, including rules on consent for cookies and spam regulations.

Together, these two laws aim to protect individuals' privacy in the context of both general data processing (GDPR) and electronic communications (ePrivacy Directive).

III. GDPR Compliance: Legal Grounds and Consent for Personal Data Processing⁵:

- The GDPR applies to the processing of personal data regardless of the means used, whether automated (e.g. an app, a website, a network of sensors) or not automated (e.g. a filing system based on paper).
- Personal data cannot be processed without a legal ground or the agreement of the data subject. This usually entails that the data subject has to give his/her consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes. However, in reality, consent is used only exceptionally if no other legal ground for processing can be found.
- Consent should be free, unambiguous, informed, prior and demonstrable by the data controller, meaning that it must be documented somehow (also electronically, e.g. by means of a log).
- In any event, data subjects must be informed about the processing undergone by their personal data before the processing starts or, when data are not collected from the data subjects themselves, within a reasonable period, in any event no later than the first communication or the first disclosure to the public.
- Data protection principles (i.e. data minimization, purpose limitation, data accuracy, storage limitation etc.) must always be respected; a data controller may have a legal ground to process personal data (e.g. the data subject's consent), yet it may still run the processing in breach of one of the key data protection principles, which would make the personal data processing

⁵ GDPR.eu, "Chapter 2 of the GDPR," accessed on Oct. 11, 2024, <https://gdpr.eu/tag/chapter-2/>

unlawful and, potentially, trigger a sanction by competent authorities. This is the essence of the principle of accountability.

- Risky processing for the data subjects requires a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA). In particular, the DPIA shall be carried out in the case of:
 - a. a systematic and extensive evaluation of personal aspects relating to natural persons which is based on automated processing, including profiling, and on which decisions are based that produce legal effects concerning the natural person or similarly significantly affect the natural person (e.g. when an insurance company uses data drawn from collected cars to build customers' profiles and premiums);
 - b. processing on a large scale of special categories of data (e.g. in the case of provision of e-health services);
 - c. a systematic monitoring of a publicly accessible area on a large scale (e.g. smart cities deploying cameras on the streets). However, it is recommended to perform a DPIA before starting any data collection from data subjects in any pilots.
- Clear procedures must be in place to ensure data subjects' rights, namely:
 - Right of access,
 - Right to rectification,
 - Right to erasure,
 - Right to restriction,
 - Right to data portability,
 - Right to object.
- Procedures to handle and notify Data Breaches to Data Protection Authorities and Data Subjects concerned must be in place.
- Data subjects should be allowed to give their consent to certain areas of scientific research when in keeping with recognized ethical standards for scientific research. Data subjects should have the opportunity to give their consent only to certain areas of research or parts of research projects to the extent allowed by the intended purpose.
- Data collected on the data subject should be strictly necessary for the specific purpose previously determined by the data controller (the "data minimization" principle).
- The purpose for which the data were collected or further processed determines the length of time for which the data should be kept. Once the data are no longer needed, they should either be deleted or kept in anonymous form if they serve historical, statistical or scientific uses.
- In cases of secondary processing of research and scientific data previously obtained for other research purposes can be used in so far as they are not incompatible. Further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes should be considered to be compatible lawful processing operations.

The GDPR intends to protect personal data processed by legal entities. As a consequence:

- It does not apply to personal data collected by individuals for their private use.
- It does not apply to data that cannot be linked to individuals. For instance, data provided by a temperature sensor fixed on a street light will not be considered as personal data (there is no

link with a natural person), while the geolocation data and sensors data collected from a smart phone will be considered as a personal data, because they can be linked to a person.

Sensitive Tools Used under GDPR:

This project does not entail to use any ethically sensitive tools, except for cloud storage and computing services. Personal and private data will not be shared.

We are not planning to implement Artificial Intelligence (AI) at this time; however, if we do decide to use it in the future, we will address it accordingly.

Data Management Plan

The privacy and management of data collected during the RIS4SEB project are comprehensively addressed in the project deliverable D1.2 – Data Management Plan. This document provides detailed procedures for handling, storing, and sharing data in a manner that respects privacy regulations and ethical standards. All project members are required to familiarize themselves with this plan and follow its guidelines to prevent any breaches.

3. General approach and rules

A. What to do if Ethics or Privacy breach is identified?

If any RIS4SEB partner identifies an ethics or privacy issue or breach at any point during the project, they should immediately notify the coordinator at VSE. The coordinator will then present the matter to the Steering Committee for further action. You can contact the coordinators at ris4seb@vse.cz.

B. Responsible body

The body responsible for ethics is the Steering committee, under the WP1.

C. Ethics advisement

Under WP1, all members will consult with their institutional ethics boards about any issues which could not be solved by the Steering committee, or if advice is needed.

D. Privacy Management advisement

Under WP1, all members will consult with their Data Protection Officer about any issues which could not be solved by the Steering committee, or if advice is needed.

4. Specific approaches at partners' institutions

Each consortium partner institution involved in the RIS4SEB project has established rules and regulations related to ethics and privacy. These regulations must be adhered to throughout the project. This guide provides a summary of the primary rules and protocols, but consortium partners are expected to continue following their institutional guidelines in addition to the RIS4SEB project rules.

A. Ethics & Protection of Personal Data at VSE⁶

This document outlines the approach of the Prague University of Economics and Business (VSE) to ethics rules and the processing and protection of personal data.

(1) Ethics

VSE has an **Ethics Committee**⁷ that is established in compliance with the Ethical Codes of VSE.

The main goal of the Ethics Committee is to ensure that all academic and research activities adhere to the highest ethical standards. This involves:

1. **Oversight of Ethical Standards:** The committee monitors compliance with ethical principles and guidelines in research and academic practices, ensuring that all activities respect the rights and dignity of individuals involved.
2. **Protection of Participants:** The committee is dedicated to safeguarding the welfare of research participants, especially vulnerable groups, by promoting transparency, informed consent, and confidentiality.
3. **Promotion of Integrity and Accountability:** The committee fosters a culture of integrity and accountability within the university community, encouraging the responsible conduct of research and ethical decision-making.
4. **Compliance with Regulations:** The committee ensures that VSE's activities comply with relevant national and international laws, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
5. **Advisory Role:** The committee provides guidance and support to faculty, researchers, and students on ethical issues, helping to navigate complex ethical dilemmas that may arise in their work.

Furthermore, VSE has established an **Ethics Committee for Research**⁸. Its main responsibilities include:

⁶ Source: internal regulations at VSE

⁷ <https://www.vse.cz/english/about-vse/university-bodies-faculties-departments/ethics-committee/>

⁸ <https://fba.vse.cz/science/science-and-research-at-fba/ethics-committee-for-research/>

- **Review and Approval:** The committee reviews research proposals to ensure they comply with ethical standards and guidelines. This includes assessing the potential impact on participants, the integrity of the research design, and the adherence to legal and institutional requirements.
- **Monitoring Compliance:** The committee monitors ongoing research projects to ensure compliance with approved ethical protocols. It may conduct periodic reviews and audits to ensure that researchers adhere to the guidelines set forth during the initial approval process.
- **Protection of Participants:** The committee is dedicated to safeguarding the rights and welfare of research participants, particularly vulnerable populations. It ensures that informed consent processes are transparent and that participants are fully aware of their rights and the nature of the research.
- **Promotion of Ethical Standards:** The committee promotes awareness and understanding of ethical standards among researchers, faculty, and students. It provides training and resources to help the university community navigate ethical dilemmas in research.
- **Advisory Role:** The committee serves as a resource for researchers seeking guidance on ethical issues. It offers support and advice on best practices in research ethics and helps researchers address ethical challenges that may arise during their projects.
- **Compliance with Regulations:** The committee ensures that VSE's research activities comply with relevant national and international laws, including the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).
- **Reporting Violations:** The committee is responsible for investigating reported ethical violations or concerns within research activities and taking appropriate actions, which may include disciplinary measures if necessary.

(2) Protection of Personal Data

i. Commitment to Personal Data Protection

VSE places significant emphasis on the ethical handling and protection of personal data. Personal data are processed only to the extent necessary for the university's operations and the provision of its services. The institution safeguards personal data in accordance with the highest legal and regulatory standards, ensuring comprehensive security measures are in place.

The key principles of personal data processing at VSE are defined under **Directive No. SR 05/2018**⁹, which reflects GDPR principles:

- This directive is **based on Regulation (EU) No 2016/679**¹⁰ of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation) (hereinafter referred to as 'the Regulation'), and Act No. 110/2019 Coll., on the processing of personal data (hereinafter referred to as 'the Adaptation Act') and

⁹ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/ochrana-a-zpracovani-osobnich-udaju-3/>

¹⁰ <https://www.vse.cz/english/about-vse/information-and-regulations/further-regulations/gdpr/>

Act No. 111/2019 Coll., which amends certain laws in connection with the adoption of the Act on the processing of personal data, complementing and elaborating on some of their provisions for the regulation of relations within VSE and establishing organizational solutions within VSE to ensure their implementation.

ii. The Register¹¹

For the purpose of obtaining an overview of personal data processing at VSE, a register of personal data processing activities (hereinafter referred to as "**the register**") is established. The operation of this register is entrusted to the Information Systems Center of VSE (hereinafter referred to as CI). The Director of CI is responsible for the operation of the register. The director of CI determines the workplaces and functional positions of the personnel responsible for the operation of the system.

iii. Operation and Use of CN and CR (PR 1/2027)¹²

A computer network (hereinafter referred to as **CN**) refers to a collection of communication technologies that allow the electronic information technology resources connected to this network to exchange information electronically. Its components include active network elements and transmission media owned by or used by VSE for its needs.

The computing resources of VSE (hereinafter referred to as **CR**) refer to a collection of electronic information technologies, primarily computers, data storage, software, and other technical resources owned by VSE or connected to and used within the CN.

The Prague University of Economics and Business owns, manages, and develops its CN and CR for the purpose of ensuring and supporting education, supporting the activities of the university's departments, and supporting the work of employees and students in fulfilling their academic obligations to the extent determined by the actual needs of individual activities, while respecting the limitations arising from the given technical and organizational possibilities.

Commercial use of the CN and CR is only possible based on a written contractual agreement following prior consultation with the Administrator of the CN and CR.

iv. Rules for the Operation and Use of Information Systems (PR 2/2023)¹³

This university directive establishes the rules for the operation, use of the university information system, and the handling of personal data contained within it. The directive follows PR 01/2007 and other internal regulations of VSE.

¹¹ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/ochrana-a-zpracovani-osobnich-udaju-3/>

¹² <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/provozovani-a-vyuzivani-vyocetni-techniky-a-pocitacove-site-vysoke-skoly-ekonomicke-v-praze/>

¹³ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/pravidla-provozovani-a-vyuzivani-informacnich-systemu-na-vysoke-skoly-ekonomicke-v-praze-2/>

The rules apply to all employees and students of VSE, to legal entities performing activities for VSE on a contractual basis, and to all other users of VSE's information systems.

The following internal regulations are closely related to this directive:

- Rector's directive PR 01/2007 on the Operation and Use of Computer Technology and Computer Network at VSE,
- Directive SR 5/2018 on the Protection and Processing of Personal Data,
- Directive SR 6/2021 on Ensuring Cybersecurity at the University of Economics in Prague.

v. Cyber Security (SR 6/2021)¹⁴

To ensure a unified Information Security Management System (hereinafter referred to as 'ISMS') and the related oversight of its compliance within VSE, the roles of Cybersecurity Manager and the Cybersecurity Management Committee of the University are established for the implementation and fulfilment of the requirements of Act No. 181/2014 Coll., on Cybersecurity and on Amendments to Related Laws (Cybersecurity Act), and its implementing legal regulations or in direct connection with them.

vi. Rules for the Operation of Email (SR 4/2019)¹⁵

- The email system at VSE is intended for fulfilling users' work and study obligations.
- These rules specify the regulations PR 1/2007 on the Operation and Use of Computer Technology and Computer Networks and SR 5/2018 on the Protection and Processing of Personal Data.
- The email system is operated by the Information Systems Center in accordance with PR 7/2018 Rules for the Operation and Use of the University Information System of VSE. Information about email and contact details for handling individual requests are provided on the Information Systems Center website.
- The operation of the email system is monitored and recorded by the operator for the purposes of:
 - o Meeting the legal obligations under Act No. 127/2005 Coll., on Electronic Communications, as amended, and Decree No. 357/2012 Coll., on the Retention, Transfer, and Disposal of Operational and Location Data.
 - o Preventing unauthorized access and misuse of the computer network and computing resources.
 - o Protecting property and ensuring the security of computing technology, with automated checks for harmful code (viruses) and detection of unsolicited emails (SPAM). Suspicious files and messages are stored in quarantine and used by the operator solely to improve antivirus and antispam control.
 - o Addressing incidents that threaten the property and interests of the university (automated forwarding of emails outside VSE's systems).

¹⁴ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/zajisteni-kyberneticke-bezpecnosti-vysoke-skoly-ekonomicke-v-praze/>

¹⁵ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/pravidla-provozu-elektronicke-posty-na-vysoke-skole-ekonomicke-v-praze-2/>

- Optimizing the operation of the email system.

vii. Rules for the Use of the server webhosting.vse.cz (PR 04/2019)¹⁶

The server at vse.cz hosts third and fourth-level domain websites and personal pages for employees of VSE. The university holds all domain names, which must comply with technical constraints and avoid infringing on public morals or existing VSE names. Domains are allocated for a fixed period through an electronic registration form, subject to approval by designated VSE officials. Personal pages are created based on an electronic form, with pages in the format <https://name.vse.cz/lastname>, automatically generated from the applicant's email. The Information Systems Center manages these pages, with access limited to those with a valid InSIS account (Information System for Students and Staff). Domains and personal pages must follow VSE's visual identity and cannot be altered by administrators. The server is monitored for security, with any misuse potentially leading to page suspension. Administrators are responsible for the content and must address any damages or compliance issues. The server supports HTTPS for secure communication and does not allow mail reception. Backups are managed by domain or page administrators.

viii. Records Management Code (SR 4/2020)¹⁷

The Records Management Code of VSE standardizes and establishes procedures for records management by the university's departments. This includes the receipt, registration, labelling, distribution, circulation, sending, processing, storage, and disposal of official documents received or created at VSE, as well as the procedures for transferring documents to the relevant archival authority, which is the State District Archive in Prague (hereinafter referred to as "the Archive").

The procedures outlined in this directive are based on Act No. 499/2004 Coll., on Archives and Records Management and on Amendments to Some Laws, as amended, Decree No. 645/2004 Coll., implementing certain provisions of the Archives and Records Management Act, Decree No. 259/2012 Coll., on the Details of Records Management, and also take into account the obligations set by Act No. 110/2019 Coll., on the Processing of Personal Data and on Amendments to Some Laws, the Ministry of the Interior's Announcement publishing the national standard for electronic records management systems VMV No. 57/2017 (hereinafter referred to as "NSESSS"), and other specific legal regulations.

VSE performs records management electronically using the Electronic Records Management System of VSE (hereinafter referred to as "eSSL AthenA").

ix. Legal Basis for Data Processing

VSE processes personal data under the following legal bases:

a. Fulfilment of Legal Obligations

¹⁶ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/pravidla-pouzivani-serveru-webhosting-vse-cz-3/>

¹⁷ <https://www.vse.cz/predpisy/spisovy-rad-vse/>

The university is required to process personal data to comply with various legal obligations, including:

- **Act No. 111/1998 Coll.** on Higher Education Institutions
- **Act No. 130/2002 Coll.** on the Support of Research and Development from Public Funds
- **Act No. 262/2006 Coll.** Labour Code
- **Act No. 563/1991 Coll.** on Accounting
- **Act No. 127/2005 Coll.** on Electronic Communications
- **Act No. 480/2004 Coll.** on certain Information Society Services
- **Act No. 181/2014 Coll.** on Cybersecurity

b. Contract Performance

Personal data are necessary for entering into and fulfilling contractual relationships. This includes processing data required before the contract is finalized.

c. Legitimate Interests of the Controller

VSE's legitimate interests include, but are not limited to:

- Protection of university assets and fraud prevention.
- Internal administrative and operational purposes, including the transfer of data within university units.
- Ensuring the security of VSE's computer network and information systems.

d. Consent of the Data Subject

In cases where personal data are processed based on the explicit consent of the data subject, VSE ensures that consent is obtained for one or more clearly defined purposes.

x. Ethical Oversight and Compliance

VSE recognizes the importance of ethical considerations in personal data management. The university's approach to personal data protection not only ensures compliance with GDPR but also reflects a commitment to uphold ethical standards in every aspect of data processing. VSE team members adhere to these rules and regulations as part of their responsibilities.

B. Ethics & Protection of Personal Data at KTU

This document outlines the approach of the Kaunas University of Technology (KTU) to ethics rules and the processing and protection of personal data.

(1) Ethics

KTU has a **Board of Academic Ethics**¹⁸ established in compliance with the **Code of Academic Ethics**¹⁹. KTU recognizes the Great Charter of European Universities, the European Charter for Researchers, the declarations and principles of the European higher education and research area, and develops and respects competences, professionalism, initiative, a sense of duty and responsibility. The main goal of the Board of Academic Ethics is to supervise and implement academic ethics at the university.

1. The Board responds to the **violations of academic ethics** in accordance with the [Code of Academic Ethics](#) approved by the Senate; it examines the statements of KTU employees and students regarding the violations of scientific, professional, communication and behavioural ethics.
2. The Board promotes the provisions of academic ethics in KTU community, **does not tolerate** discrimination based on the person's sex, age, ethnicity, nationality or social background, religion or beliefs, sexual orientation, language, disability, political views, social or economic status, **does not tolerate** violations of moral and property rights of the institution's intellectual property and copyrights, plagiarism and other forms of academic dishonesty.
3. The Board does not examine the misconducts of KTU employees that are examined under the procedure set by the Code of Labor, as well as the academic misconducts of students and unclassified students that are examined under the procedure set by the [Academic Regulations](#).
4. The Board does not undertake to respond to every letter; however, clearly motivated statements and complaints will be examined in its meetings. Anonymous letters are not examined.

KTU has established a **Research Ethics Commission**²⁰. The Research Ethics Commission of Kaunas University of Technology assesses applications submitted by the university's employees or doctoral students to conduct an ethical assessment of the planned research which **involves human participants** (except research that falls within the scope of bioethics*) or includes **the collection and/or processing of personal data**.

** When planning the biomedical research, which involves humans or their groups, embryos, organs, cells and genetic material, corpses, medical documents as the objects of research, it is required to apply to the Lithuanian Bioethics Committee or the regional (Vilnius or Kaunas) biomedical research ethics committee.*

The Commission is set up to protect and defend human rights, freedoms and dignity in the research involving human participants (except for the research falling in the scope of bioethics) or including the collection and/or processing of personal data. The Commission performs the following functions:

¹⁸ [Board of Academic Ethics – Kaunas University of Technology | KTU](#)

¹⁹ [Akademinės etikos kodeksas | Kauno technologijos universitetas | KTU](#)

²⁰ [Research Ethics - Kaunas University of Technology | KTU](#)

- **Review and Approval:** Examines the Applications and provides the Approvals when the research involving human participants (except for the research falling in the scope of bioethics) or including the collection and/or processing of personal data is conducted,
- **Monitoring Compliance:** Consults the University's academic employees and doctoral students regarding the compliance of the planned research with the ethical requirements,
- **Promotion of Ethical Standards:** Educates and informs the University's academic community on the issues of research ethics.
- The Commission **does not deal with the violations of research ethics**. At the University, this function is performed by the University's Board of Academic Ethics.

The functions, structure and work organization procedure of the Commission are defined in the **Rules of Procedure of the Research Ethics Commission of Kaunas University of Technology**²¹.

The procedure for granting approval to conduct the planned research is regulated by the **Guidelines for the Assessment of Research Ethics at Kaunas University of Technology**²².

(2) Protection of Personal Data

i. Commitment to Personal Data Protection

KTU places significant emphasis on the ethical handling and protection of personal data. The Privacy Policy for the Personal Data Processed at Kaunas University of Technology²³ provides information on the principles that Kaunas University of Technology applies to the processing of the data of the members of its community and partners, the rights of the data subjects and how they can be exercised.

The concepts used in **the Privacy Policy** are interpreted in the meaning defined as follows:

- **Personal data** – any information related to a natural person whose identity is or can be identified directly or indirectly by using such data as personal ID number, one or several physical, psychological, economic, cultural or social characteristics of a person.
- **General Data Protection Regulation (hereinafter – GDPR)** – Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and Council (EU) of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regards to the processing of personal data and the free movement of such data for the protection of natural persons in the processing of personal data and repealing Directive 95/46/EC.
- **Data subject** – any natural person whose identity is or can be identified and whose personal data are processed by Kaunas University of Technology.
- **Data processing** – any action by automated or non-automated measures using the personal data: collection, recording, accumulation, storage, classification, organisation, merging with other data, creation (including creation based on other data), changing (adaptation, addition or correction), profiling, submission (transfer), publication, use, search, destruction, deletion, etc.

²¹ Source: Rules of Procedure of the Research Ethics Commission of Kaunas University of Technology, approved by Order No. A-484 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 20 October 2020

²² Source: Guidelines for the Assessment of Research Ethics at Kaunas University of Technology, approved by Order No. A-201 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 23 April 2021

²³ ktu.edu-Privatumo-politika_isakymui_EN.pdf

- **Data controller** – a legal entity or natural person who, individually or in cooperation with others, establishes the purposes and measures of data processing.
 - **Data processor** – a legal entity or natural person authorised by the data controller to process personal data. While processing data, a data processor receives the instructions from the data controller and does not establish any purposes of the processing.
 - **Joint data controllers** – the legal entities or natural persons who jointly process personal data but each of them pursues individual purposes of the processing.
 - **Special category personal data** – information on the natural person’s racial or ethnic origin, political, religious, philosophical or other beliefs, membership of trade unions, health, sexual orientation or criminal record.
 - **Consent** – specific and unambiguous expression of the properly informed data subject, given freely as a written or oral statement or by unambiguously understood actions expressing his/her consent for the processing of the related personal data.
 - **Direct marketing** – the activities of offering to the persons the services of the University and/or ask for their opinion on the provided services by mail, telephone or in another direct method. The personal data processing for the purposes of marketing requires s data subject’s consent.
- Other definitions used in the Privacy Policy have the same meaning as in the GDPR or other applicable legislation.

The KTU’s employees or other data processors duly authorised by the University process personal data according to the following principles: **lawfulness, fairness and transparency; purpose limitation; data minimisation; accuracy; storage limitation; integrity and confidentiality, accountability**. KTU processes the personal data based on the following legal grounds defined by the GDPR.

ii. Registration

Kaunas University of Technology has implemented a solution for electronic identity management and unified access to KTU information systems and information technology (IT) services. All employees and students are provided KTU IT user credentials. Applicants, dormitory residents, emeriti and KTU guests are provided IT user credentials with restricted access to University IT services. From July 2024, two-factor authentication (2FA) is activated for KTU IT users connecting to any University system using KTU unified login²⁴.

iii. IT security policy of the Kaunas University of Technology

The IT Security Policy of Kaunas University of Technology²⁵ outlines the principles of information security and the procedures for their implementation. **The primary goal of this policy is to achieve an adequate level of IT information security across the University's infrastructure and information systems.**

It aims to protect personal data and ensure a safe working environment for KTU employees, maintaining the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of information and information systems. The

²⁴ [Registration and passwords](#)

²⁵ Source: IT security policy of the Kaunas University of Technology, approved by Order No. A-624 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 10 October 2020 KTU rector's order No. A-624 on 10 December 2020

policy also sets forth basic information security requirements. Adherence to the requirements specified in this policy ensures the effective protection of the University's information resources and promotes their uninterrupted and efficient use. The provisions of this policy apply to all KTU employees who utilize information resources. The IT Security Department of KTU's Information Technology Department is responsible for implementing the provisions of this policy.

iv. Regulations for access to information technology resources of Kaunas University of Technology

The regulations governing access to the information technology resources at Kaunas University of Technology (KTU)²⁶ outline the processes for granting and revoking access. **These regulations are designed to ensure the efficient and safe use of KTU's information technology resources.** Access and administration of these resources are managed by the Department of Information Technology, which is also responsible for implementing technical measures to control access effectively.

v. Guidelines for users of the KTU computer network

Kaunas University of Technology offers its employees and students access to information technologies and internet resources through KTU's computer network²⁷. The KTU values personal communication, recognizes the diversity of perspectives typical in the academic community, and respects the privacy of all members within the KTU community. Each user of the KTU computer network is responsible for their actions while utilizing the University's network. **These guidelines outline the principles for the ethical, legal, and secure use of computers and computer networks for all users.** Violations of these guidelines may threaten the university and the operation of its computer systems. All users of KTU's computer network resources - employees, students, visitors, and personnel from third parties using KTU equipment - must adhere to these rules. These guidelines apply whenever using KTU's computer network or equipment leased to the university.

vi. Information security cyber incident management procedure of Kaunas University of Technology

The information security cyber incident management procedure at Kaunas University of Technology²⁸ outlines the steps taken by the Information Technology Security Department at the KTU Computer Network Centre to effectively manage cyber incidents identified within the University's information systems. This procedure does not apply to the information systems managed by the University Internet Service Centre.

In the course of managing these incidents, KTU collects various types of data, including:

- The time the cyber incident was recorded
- The IP addresses of the participants involved in the incident
- The ports used by the incident participants

²⁶ Source: Regulations for access to information technology resources of Kaunas University of Technology, approved by Order No. A-472 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 15 November 2021

²⁷ Source: Guidelines for users of the KTU computer network, approved by Order No. A-357 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 6 June 2008

²⁸ Source: Description of the information security cyber incident management procedure of Kaunas University of Technology, approved by Order No. A-197 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 8 May 2020

- Information from the incident participants regarding the vulnerability of the service
- The name and surname of the information system owner
- The email address of the system owner

Personal data gathered during the management of information security cyber incidents may only be shared with third parties according to the procedures established by the laws and regulations of the Republic of Lithuania.

Data related to cyber incidents that occur at the University, along with any relevant technical records, is stored for a minimum of six months. This retention period complies with the personal data storage guidelines set forth by the General Data Protection Regulation and the University's data storage policy.

vii. Information system data security regulations

The information system data security regulations of Kaunas University of Technology²⁹ outline the objectives for maintaining the security of electronic information within the University's managed information systems. These regulations specify organizational and technical requirements, qualifications for personnel, and the principles for familiarizing system managers, handlers, and users with security documents.

When managing electronic information in information systems and ensuring its safety (cyber security), the following legal acts are used:

- Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
- Law on Legal Protection of Personal Data of the Republic of Lithuania
- Law on Electronic Communications of the Republic of Lithuania
- Law on Cyber Security of the Republic of Lithuania
- Law on State Information Resources Management of the Republic of Lithuania
- Directive (EU) 2022/2555 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 December 2022 on measures for a high common level of cybersecurity across the Union, amending Regulation (EU) No 910/2014 and Directive (EU) 2018/1972, and repealing Directive (EU) 2016/1148 (NIS 2 Directive) (Text with EEA relevance)
- Resolution No. 716 "On the approval of the description of the general requirements for the security of electronic information and the description of the guidelines for the content of security documents" of the Government of the Republic of Lithuania of 24 July 2013

viii. Procedure for providing the official electronic mail service of Kaunas University of Technology

²⁹ Source: Information system data security regulations, approved by Order No. A-277 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 4 June 2024

The procedure for providing email services at Kaunas University of Technology³⁰ outlines the conditions under which KTU offers this service to its community, including students, listeners, employees, and other individuals directly associated with the University's activities.

- KTU email is intended for official correspondence related to work functions, as well as, for sharing information pertinent to studies, scientific research, and social activities. The KTU study, science and administration departments communicate important information to students, listeners, and employees via the official email addresses assigned by the University.
- The service is managed by the Department of Information Technology at KTU, which is responsible for email setup, maintenance, and deletion of email accounts. This includes managing access rights to email mailboxes. The service operates within the University Data Center's infrastructure and the Microsoft cloud environment, and the data are stored in the European Union.
- KTU is responsible for the personal data of its community members associated with their email accounts, ensuring the legality of the data collection and publication. In providing this service, KTU acts as a data controller and collects data such as each user's unique university number, first name, last name, the exact time of specific events, the name of the service station used for connections, the protocol used to connect, the IP address, and the email addresses to which communications were sent or delivered.
- Any personal data collected during the service may only be shared with third parties following the legal procedures established by the laws of the Republic of Lithuania.

ix. Domain registration procedure of Kaunas University of Technology

The domain name creation procedure of the Kaunas University of Technology regulates the creation and management of the University's domain names³¹. The procedure is prepared in accordance with LT domain procedural regulation; EDU domain policy; KTU statute. The Internet Services Centre of the Department of Information Technology administers KTU domains and maintains the domain name register. The domain name is registered in the University's common (KTU.LT and KTU.EDU) domain register. Domain names of university websites must be used in the KTU.EDU domain and the KTU.LT domain can only be activated after coordination with the Marketing and Communication Department. Domain names intended for other purposes (not websites) are activated in KTU.LT, and if desired, in the KTU.EDU domain. KTU domain names are associated only with University IP addresses. In special cases, at the request of a university unit, third-level and lower-level domain names may be associated with third-party IP addresses in coordination with the Department of Information Technology. Names of fourth-level or lower-level domains intended for university departments, projects, or other purposes (except for websites) are registered after the Internet Service Centre receives a request from the person responsible for the registered domain, approved by the person responsible for the higher-level domain. The Internet Service Centre does not register the domain name and informs the responsible person who submitted the request, indicating the reason for the rejection of the request,

³⁰ Source: Description of the procedure for providing the official electronic mail service of Kaunas University of technology, approved by Order No. A-76 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 9 February 2024

³¹ Source: Description of the domain name creation procedure of the Kaunas University of Technology, approved by Order No. A-110 of the Rector of Kaunas University of Technology of 13 March 2015

if the domain name specified in the request contradicts the requirements set out in the Procedure Description.

x. Ethical Oversight and Compliance

KTU recognizes the importance of ethical considerations in personal data management. The University's approach to personal data protection not only ensures compliance with GDPR but also reflects a commitment to uphold ethical standards in every aspect of data processing. KTU team members adhere to these rules and regulations as part of their responsibilities.

C. Ethics & Protection of Personal Data at EBS

(1) Ethics

The ethical standards at EBS are outlined in the [EBS Code of Academic Ethics](#). However, its section on research ethics (Section 4) is quite concise, comprising only the following three clauses:

4.1 At every stage of research, the author must remain honest. As a supervisor and reviewer, they must refrain from any form of misrepresentation, such as fabricating or falsifying data, plagiarising others works, disregarding the work, data or protocols of other authors and disregarding confidentiality requirements.

4.2 Research in which people form the object of research must not contravene the principle of human dignity or basic human rights.

4.3 In all research work in which the subjects under study are people, it is mandatory to inform those being studied of the nature of the research (its aim and methodology, how its results will be used and how the data from the research will be protected), their right to withdraw at any time, their right to forbid the use of their data, etc.

EBS has also endorsed the [EURAXESS' Code of Conduct](#) as well as the [European Charter of Researchers](#). Along with all other Estonian universities, it has also signed the [quality agreement for doctoral studies](#), adopted the [EBS Guidelines for Using AI Chatbots for Teaching and Studies](#), and the [Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion plan 2022-2025](#).

While these documents provide some ethical guidance, it is evident that most were developed and adopted for purposes other than research, and they require significant expansion and updates. Fortunately, the Estonian government is in the process of reforming its Act on the Organisation of Research, Development, and Innovation. As part of this reform, the Ministry of Education and Research has drafted new regulations for the Governance of Research Ethics (*Teaduseetika korraldus*), which have already undergone an initial round of discussions with stakeholders, including EBS and is expected to be signed by the Minister later this academic year.

Once the key decisions regarding these regulations are finalized, EBS will have clearer guidance on how to proceed. One option may be for EBS to establish its own Research Ethics Committee, complete with all necessary documentation and institutional capacity to guide and review applications, and, if needed, to act as an arbiter. Alternatively, the Estonian Research Council may take on this role centrally or find a way to support the existing Research Ethics Committees at the University of Tartu and/or the Health Development Institute, which currently fulfill this function.

Furthermore, a dedicated plan to educate researchers and PhD students on identifying research ethics issues and minimizing risks is currently being developed.

(2) Protection of Personal Data

To safeguard personal data and ensure compliance with relevant regulations, EBS has adopted the Privacy Terms and Cookies Policy, which can be found [here](#). Additionally, the school also has EBS Data Management Policy that is soon to be updated.

D. Ethics & Protection of Personal Data at UB

(1) Ethics

Bocconi University considers ethics, as well as responsibility for one's conduct and actions as essential for people's education and professional lives. This is why Bocconi publishes and circulates an Honor Code and Code of Conduct for Students and Faculty with the objective of conveying and reinforcing the values of commitment and propriety which are essential in carrying out study, research and professional activities within the entire Bocconi community.

The Honor Code gives importance to, organizes and makes transparent the rules about conduct and penalty procedures which are largely already laid out in national university regulations and by Bocconi University.

Regarding to research the honor code states the following principles:

Accountability

While conducting their research, the faculty is ultimately accountable to the University and the general public and should act accordingly. Faculty members should ensure the highest standards of impartiality and methodological accuracy in carrying out research and reporting results, and in particular:

- Be able to justify the design of research and to reliably explain how results were reached;
- When using data, explain the empirical methodology, report evidence fully, and make third-party replication possible;
- Substantiate claims to originality and attribute proper credit to pre-existing work;
- Consider any risk that research outcomes might produce for Bocconi University and society. Whenever faculty members become aware of potential risks, they should take active steps to minimize them.

Respect

Faculty members should respect the dignity of the individuals and organizations they study, and in particular:

- Abide by the requirements of the Ethical Review Procedure issued by the Bocconi Research Ethics Committee with regard to the protection of research participants
- Recognize and manage potential harm for others relating to their research
- Maximize the benefits of research to participants and society

- Manage and preserve research data effectively for a reasonable period of time in accordance with good research practices.

Transparency

Faculty members should always act lawfully and honestly, and in particular:

- Disclose in their research products any direct or indirect financial support they received for the specific investigation as well as any conflict of interest that might compromise the impartiality of the analysis
- Accept their duty to publish and disseminate research in a manner that reports the findings accurately and without misleading selection.

Bocconi University also set up a dedicated Research Ethics Committee. The Committee – created by Rectoral Decree in July 2013 has been created to guarantee that research activities respect fundamental ethics principles, including those reflected in the [Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union](#).

(2) Protection of Personal Data

To safeguard personal data and ensure compliance with relevant regulations, UB has adopted the Privacy Terms and Policy, which can be found at the following address: [Faculty & Staff Privacy Policy - Bocconi University](#).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the D1.3 – Ethics & Privacy Management Plan establishes a comprehensive framework to guide the RIS4SEB project's practices in safeguarding personal data and ensuring ethical conduct. By adhering to the outlined policies and procedures, the project consortium demonstrates a strong commitment to protecting the privacy and rights of individuals while upholding the highest standards of integrity and transparency.

This approach emphasizes compliance with relevant regulations, such as GDPR, and industry best practices, offering clear guidelines for handling sensitive information. Robust measures for risk assessment, data protection, and ethical decision-making have been implemented, ensuring that all actions align with legal requirements and organizational values. If any RIS4SEB partner identifies an ethics or privacy issue or breach at any point during the project, they are required to promptly notify the coordinator at VSE, who will present the matter to the Steering Committee for resolution.

The Ethics & Privacy Management Plan not only ensures compliance with relevant laws but also fosters a culture of trust and accountability across the project. This proactive approach to transparency, respect for individual rights, and ethical responsibility underpins the RIS4SEB project's mission of enhancing synergies and capacity-building within the European Research Area. Maintaining trust and accountability requires ongoing vigilance and adaptation, and the consortium is dedicated to continuously upholding these principles.

Through this plan, the RIS4SEB project protects the privacy of individuals, reinforces its reputation as a trusted and ethical entity, and sets a strong foundation for sustainable and responsible progress toward its objectives. This dedication reflects the project's overarching commitment to fostering a secure and respectful environment for all stakeholders while contributing to the long-term success and impact of its international research initiatives.